

LEARNING ACCESSIBILITY AND SUSTAINABILITY THROUGH IMMERSIVE EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCES: THE CROMA-GREENSCENT METHODOLOGY

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Abstract

The urgency of the climate crisis requires environmental education and communication to be accessible to all, including those with disabilities. In the absence of comprehensive access to climate change education and information, certain groups face marginalisation, which not only places them at risk but also hinders their involvement in environmental initiatives. To address this need, the CROMA-GreenSCENT methodology was developed. This educational methodology integrates accessibility, sustainability, and educational engagement through a pilot program designed to provide inclusive learning experiences. It was developed through a collaboration between the CROMA programme, which targets socio-economically disadvantaged primary school students in the Barcelona area, and the GreenSCENT Horizon 2020 project, which leverages digital tools to promote environmental awareness across multiple European countries. The CROMA-GreenSCENT methodology is structured into three distinct phases. The first phase comprises initial training sessions for trainers focusing on accessibility and sustainability by experts in both fields. This is subsequently followed by an implementation phase, during which trainers facilitate six interactive sessions using digital tools like 360-degree cameras, where students engage as researchers to craft immersive, accessible stories about their school's sustainability. The programme concludes with a feedback and evaluation phase to assess educational impacts and refine the methodology. Throughout all three phases, trainers maintain interaction with researchers to receive ongoing feedback and support when needed. This paper delves into the development and implementation of the methodology over these three phases and presents recommendations based on the learning and insights gained from the programme.

Keywords: Environmental Education, Accessibility, Sustainability, Inclusion, Immersive Education.

1 INTRODUCTION

Integrating accessibility into environmental education is crucial to ensuring that everyone, including individuals with disabilities, can access information about the climate crisis and environmental issues, raising awareness about the importance of inclusive climate communication that leaves no one behind [1]. Individuals with disabilities often face significant barriers in accessing information and participating in climate discussions [2], which heightens their vulnerability to environmental changes. These challenges also conflict with the principles of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD), which emphasises the need for full inclusion of people with disabilities in all aspects of society, including the development of environmental policies and actions [3].

In 2021, the Council of the European Union published a resolution highlighting the crucial role of education in fostering a future Europe that is inclusive, sustainable, and environmentally conscious [4]. This initiative led to the enactment of Real Decreto 157/2022 in Spain, aimed at renewing the national education curriculum to meet these goals [5]. However, an analysis of the new curriculum in Catalonia, the region where the following case study is based, reveals a gap: while sustainability is deeply integrated into all primary school subjects, there is a notable absence of references to accessibility and disability. To bridge this gap, the development of educational methodologies that incorporate both sustainability and accessibility is essential [6].

The CROMA-GreenSCENT methodology emerges as a direct response to this need. This pilot project, born from a collaboration between the CROMA programme and the GreenSCENT project, aims to make environmental education accessible to all by embedding principles of accessibility, inclusion, and sustainability within the educational curriculum. The CROMA programme is aimed at supporting primary school students aged 10 to 12 from the Barcelona area who experience educational and socio-economic challenges. Its goal is to boost their engagement and interest in learning about accessibility and sustainability through interactive workshops, which are led by university students from the Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB) [7]. These UAB students receive prior training that equips them with

innovative pedagogical tools, alongside essential knowledge in accessibility and sustainability, allowing them to serve as effective trainers. The programme, therefore, serves a dual purpose: it offers UAB students valuable teaching experience and educational skills as trainers, while enriching the learning experience of the primary school students who participate in the workshops. The GreenSCENT project is a three-year European initiative aimed at enhancing accessible environmental education through the use of digital tools. It targets a diverse audience, including students from primary schools, universities, and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). When combined, these initiatives have contributed to the development of the three-steps CROMA-GreenSCENT methodology, which involves a structured pilot programme:

- 1 **Initial training sessions:** conducted by researchers in accessibility and sustainability, this training was divided into two sessions. The first session focused on enhancing trainers' awareness of the connection between accessibility and sustainability. The second, more hands-on session, showed trainers how to engage students in activities that combine these themes, using digital tools such as 360 cameras.
- 2 **Implementation phase:** this phase involved trainers delivering the educational content over six interactive sessions to students. Using the digital tools (360 cameras) and pedagogical strategies introduced during the initial training, these sessions aimed to deepen students' understanding of how accessibility and sustainability are interconnected.
- 3 **Feedback and evaluation phase:** the final phase included one session in which trainers, students, and researchers came together to show the results of the workshop and share feedback through a questionnaire.

Figure 1: Three-steps CROMA-GreenSCENT methodology

This paper is organised to achieve three main objectives: 1) to provide an outline of the three-step CROMA-GreenSCENT methodology; 2) to analyse feedback from trainers and a coordinator, gathered through a qualitative report with quotes capturing their experiences during both the training and implementation phases; and 3) to offer recommendations and conclude with an overview of the key lessons, strengths, and challenges observed in the programme. The paper aims to serve as a resource for educators, teachers, and trainers looking to implement accessibility and sustainability in their school or extracurricular activities.

2 THEORIES GUIDING THE THREE STEPS CROMA-GREENSCENT METHODOLOGY

Before outlining the specifics of our methodology, it is important to highlight the theoretical foundations that have shaped its development. Our methodology is grounded in the socio-constructivist framework, drawing significant inspiration from the educational theory of Paulo Freire. In his influential work *Pedagogy of the Oppressed* (1970), Freire emphasises the importance of dialogue and collaboration in education. He advocates for a model where learning is a joint process between educators and learners, focused on dialogue and problem-solving, rather than the simple transmission of information from teacher to student. Freire rejected the traditional "banking model" of education, where students passively

receive knowledge. Instead, he promoted a problem-based approach, where students actively engage with the material, question it, and work through real-world issues. This approach helps to develop students' critical thinking and reflective abilities. For example, in a history class, instead of merely memorising facts, students would investigate the causes and impacts of historical events, engaging in discussions to understand their broader significance. Freire also introduced the concept of Critical Consciousness (*Conscientização*), which argues that education should empower learners to become aware of their social, political, and economic circumstances [8]. By developing this awareness, students can identify social injustices and take action to challenge oppressive structures. An example might be a community-based educational project where learners investigate local environmental issues and create campaigns to combat pollution. For Freire, education is not just about acquiring knowledge, but about liberation—helping individuals reclaim their sense of humanity and empowering them to transform their world. This form of education goes beyond literacy skills, encouraging learners to reflect on their roles in society and their potential for enacting change [8]. Freire's theory informs our methodology by promoting a dynamic, interactive learning environment. Rather than simply teaching the principles of sustainability and accessibility, these concepts are explored collaboratively through dialogue and hands-on activities. This approach ensures that our educational practices are both informative and transformative, creating an inclusive space where all participants actively contribute to and reshape their understanding of sustainability and accessibility.

Our methodology also integrates cutting-edge digital tools to enhance the educational experience, particularly through the use of 360° video cameras. This technological incorporation is based on recent research that demonstrates the effectiveness of immersive learning environments in enhancing student engagement and improving learning outcomes. Studies by Merchant et al. [9] and McDonagh & Brescia-Zapata [10] have shown that immersive digital environments can significantly enrich learning experiences by providing students with a more engaging, interactive, and realistic context for acquiring knowledge. Furthermore, the methodology embraces the principles of "Universal Design for Learning" (UDL), as proposed by Meyer, Rose, and Gordon [11]. UDL is an educational framework that supports the development of flexible learning environments that can accommodate individual learning differences. According to the authors, implementing UDL involves providing multiple means of engagement, representation, and expression to meet the diverse needs of learners, including those with disabilities. Our approach ensures that accessibility is at the forefront, enabling all participants, regardless of their abilities, to benefit fully from the educational content.

Having established the foundations that guided the development of our methodology, we will now analyse it in detail, so that this paper can serve as a guide for teachers, trainers and educators.

3 THREE-STEPS CROMA-GREENSCENT METHODOLOGY

The Croma-GreenSCENT methodology was structured into three phases. The first phase involved initial training sessions over two days: one day focused on an introduction to the thematic concepts, and the second day introduced the six-day activities that would be conducted with the students. The second phase was the implementation, where trainers carried out the six days of activities with the children. Lastly, the third phase involved gathering feedback. The following section will provide a detailed overview of each phase, its specific components, and the feedback received.

3.1 Initial training sessions

The initial phase, as previously mentioned, was divided into two sessions "Introduction to the themes" and "Educational strategies".

3.1.1 Introduction to the themes

In this initial phase, trainers were introduced to the context and purpose of the workshop, focusing on the challenges faced by individuals with disabilities during climate events. This vulnerability is often due to risk management plans and climate change communications not accommodating their diverse needs. [12]. The workshop aimed to make young people aware of these issues and inspire them to design digital content that is accessible to everyone. After establishing the context, trainers were then guided through the structure of the 6-session workshop they will be conducting for young participants. Each session revolved around the central question: "How can we collaboratively create a video on sustainability that is accessible to everyone?"

Following this, the specific objectives of the workshop were detailed:

- Increase awareness of the diverse needs of individuals.
- Explore solutions to make audiovisual content on sustainability accessible.
- Collaborate to produce a 360-degree video that includes accessibility features such as Catalan Sign Language and audio descriptions, focusing on the school environment of the students.

With this foundation set, the workshop then proceeded to the second session “Educational strategies”.

3.1.2 Educational strategies

Trainers were given an outline of the 6-day workshops they were responsible for facilitating. Each session began with a breakdown of the activities planned for that day, followed by the trainers' questions, concerns, and feedback. The 6-day workshops followed the structure detailed below:

- **Day 1:** Trainers kick off the workshop by posing the research question guiding their activities: "How can we collaboratively create a video on sustainability that is accessible to everyone?" They introduce the GreenSCENT and CROMA projects and the 360 camera, outlining its capabilities and potential for capturing sustainability stories. Participants are given time to brainstorm and define specific aspects of sustainability they wish to record. This session lays the groundwork for the days ahead, allowing students to conceptualise their projects and decide on their focus areas.
- **Day 2:** Building on the foundation laid in the first session, trainers lead students through the process of creating 360-degree videos using the cameras. They offer technical support and creative guidance to help students effectively capture their chosen sustainability stories in an immersive format. This session emphasises hands-on learning, allowing students to experiment with the equipment and develop their filmmaking skills.
- **Day 3:** Trainers introduce an additional element to the projects by asking students to incorporate 2D videos, specifically interviews with teachers or staff at their school about sustainability, into their 360-degree footage. Guidance is provided on conducting interviews, framing questions, and recording the interviews to ensure valuable insights are gathered for the projects.
- **Day 4:** This session addresses accessibility issues, introducing a new dimension to the students' understanding of their projects. Trainers show videos from individuals who faced challenges in accessing the audio content due to being hard of hearing. This prompts a discussion on solutions, such as incorporating sign language into the videos. Students learn some phrases in Catalan sign language, practice it, and integrate it into their 360 videos to make them more inclusive.
- **Day 5:** Continuing the focus on accessibility, this session addresses visual impairments. Trainers show a video from someone unable to see the content, sparking a discussion on implementing audio descriptions. Students practice creating audio descriptions and add them to their initial 360 videos to ensure accessibility for individuals with visual impairments.
- **Day 6:** The final session centres on students sharing their completed 360 videos with each other and reflecting on the entire process. Trainers facilitate a discussion on lessons learned, challenges encountered, and successes achieved throughout the project. Students also reflect on the sustainability of their school, discussing how their projects contribute to raising awareness and promoting positive change. This session provides closure to the workshop, allowing students to celebrate their accomplishments.

Throughout this session, which introduced trainers to the 6-day workshops, they were encouraged not to immediately address accessibility concerns allowing students to gradually recognise its significance through the challenges depicted in the videos. Trainers were reminded to maintain communication with researchers for assistance and to regularly submit materials. Researchers were responsible for compiling these materials and integrating them into the GreenVerse platform, a 360-storytelling tool developed by the GreenSCENT project, allowing trainers to focus solely on the training. During this second session, in addition to the 6-day workshop introduction, trainers engaged in self-training on accessibility. With the assistance of researchers, they practised audio description, learned basic phrases in Catalan sign language, and underwent simulations of low visibility and deafness. This immersive approach deepened trainers' understanding of the needs of individuals with disabilities, turning the training itself into a learning experience.

3.2 Implementation phase

Trainers carried out the six workshops presented in 3.1.2, staying in touch with researchers for guidance and assistance. After the completion of each workshop session, trainers forwarded the materials to the researchers. The researchers then began the process of collecting and organising the materials, with the goal of incorporating them into the GreenVerse platform to create a finalised story by the end of the sixth day. This collaborative effort ensured that the progress made each day was effectively captured and integrated into the final narrative of the sustainability project.

3.3 Feedback and evaluation phase

The feedback and evaluation phase, based on the qualitative report from the 4 trainers and a coordinator involved in the project, offered valuable insights into the effectiveness of the activities conducted. This feedback allowed for reflection on the project's implementation, particularly in terms of methodology, content, duration, resources, and overall impact. Below is a summary of the key points covered, including suggestions for improvement.

3.3.1 Methodologies and methods of engagement

The methodology and methods of engagement employed in the project received positive reviews from the trainers. They emphasised the success of combining dynamic and varied activities, which allowed students to gradually assimilate the information presented. The use of a 360° video as a central theme throughout the project was particularly praised, as it maintained students' motivation and provided a concrete goal. One trainer noted that *"the methodology greatly facilitated students' learning, and thanks to the variety of activities, knowledge was progressively absorbed"*. Another praised the choice to use 360° video, describing it as *"a complete success"* adding an interactive component that kept the project cohesive and focused.

The balance between individual tasks and group activities was another key success of the project. Individual tasks helped students develop autonomy and independence, while group activities promoted collaboration and mutual support. The smaller group size, typically four to six students, was particularly effective in encouraging active participation and peer learning. According to the trainers, *"Individual tasks promote autonomy, while group activities have enhanced group cohesion and mutual aid development"*. They also highlighted that the mix of individual and group learning experiences enriched the students, helping them develop a broad range of skills.

3.3.2 Content

While the content of the project was engaging overall, some challenges arose in linking certain themes, such as sustainability and accessibility. Although students were interested in the topics presented, they struggled to understand the connection between sustainability and accessibility for people with disabilities. Coordinators suggested that future iterations of the project would benefit from more integrated and coherent sessions that better connect these themes. They commented that *"the logical link between sustainability and accessibility was difficult for children to grasp"* and recommended designing activities or discussions to help bridge this gap.

3.3.3 Duration

The project's duration was generally considered appropriate, though some activities, particularly those involving audio descriptions, required more time than anticipated. The use of Virtual Reality (VR) goggles was popular among the students but did not receive enough time for full exploration. One trainer observed, *"There is consensus that the duration was adequate to meet the objectives"* but added that *"certain sessions, especially those with audio descriptions, were difficult to complete due to time constraints"*. To improve the learning experience, coordinators suggested extending the time allocated to certain activities, particularly those involving VR goggles, and improving time management to ensure that all planned sessions were fully covered.

3.3.4 Technological resources

The technological resources used in the project, including VR goggles and 360° cameras, were highly effective in capturing students' attention and encouraging curiosity. Trainers noted that these tools added a modern, interactive dimension to the project, making it more engaging. The 360° video, in particular, sparked great interest among the children. One coordinator remarked, *"The resources and*

materials used in the different activities are highly valued" while another emphasised that "the use of 360° cameras sparked genuine curiosity among the children".

3.3.5 Impact

The impact of the project was most notable in areas related to accessibility and hands-on learning. The trainers shared that students were especially motivated by the activities involving sign language and the creation of accessible materials. The practical nature of these tasks allowed students to apply their knowledge in meaningful ways, with the 360° video being a particular highlight. However, the sustainability aspect had a lesser impact compared to accessibility, and coordinators suggested making the sustainability theme more engaging in future projects. According to one coordinator, *"There is consensus that the project greatly motivated the children"* and another noted that *"they were particularly engaged with accessibility, especially learning Catalan sign language"*.

3.3.6 Spaces for improvements

In terms of improvements, the coordinators proposed several suggestions to enhance future projects. These included dedicating more time to introductory sessions on sustainability, allowing more time for interactive activities like VR goggles, and making video resources more accessible on school computers. Additionally, they recommended redesigning the audio description sessions to make them more dynamic, potentially incorporating game-like elements to better engage the students. As one coordinator suggested: *"It would be interesting to have an introductory session focused on understanding sustainability"* while another proposed *"finding a more dynamic and stimulating way to approach the session on audio descriptions"*. These improvements aim to enhance both the content and the overall student experience in future projects.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The CROMA-GreenSCENT methodology successfully combined accessibility and sustainability within environmental education through an immersive, hands-on approach. The integration of digital tools, such as 360-degree cameras, and interactive activities, including learning sign language, proved highly effective in engaging students. These tools not only captured students' attention but also motivated them to actively participate in the creation of accessible, sustainability-themed content. The hands-on nature of activities like sign language learning was particularly effective, with students expressing enthusiasm about creating inclusive digital content, especially through the use of 360-degree videos. This approach aligns with constructivist learning theories, emphasising active participation and social interaction as key drivers of student engagement.

However, feedback from trainers indicated that a significant challenge was in helping students understand the deeper connection between accessibility and sustainability. Despite the engaging nature of the activities, many students found it difficult to grasp how these two themes are interconnected. This is a common gap noted in the literature, where the intersection of social inclusion and environmental sustainability is often underexplored [13]. Students would benefit from more structured guidance and concrete examples to illustrate this connection, such as highlighting how climate change disproportionately affects marginalised communities and how inclusive communication and infrastructure are vital for ensuring equitable climate resilience. Real-world scenarios, such as emergency alarms that do not accommodate people who are hard of hearing or sustainable architecture that includes ramps and tactile paths for people with visual impairments, can help bridge this understanding gap. The "just sustainability" framework proposed by Julian Agyeman [14] could be employed here, showing students that sustainability efforts must address social equity to be truly effective. Agyeman's "just sustainability" framework provides a key perspective for addressing the gap in students' understanding of the connection between accessibility and sustainability. This framework stresses that sustainability must go beyond resource conservation and environmental protection to include social justice and equity. A truly sustainable society, according to Agyeman, ensures fair access to environmental benefits and protections for all communities, particularly those most vulnerable to environmental harms. By integrating "just sustainability" into the curriculum, students can begin to see that accessibility is a fundamental part of building a sustainable future. For instance, they can explore how sustainable development must include designs accessible to people with disabilities, ensuring that marginalised groups are not excluded from the benefits of eco-friendly technologies, infrastructure, or climate adaptation strategies. In this way, students learn that sustainability efforts must prioritize equity to ensure a greener future is inclusive and just for everyone. The challenge of connecting accessibility with sustainability underscores the importance of incorporating climate justice into educational practices. Climate justice focuses on the unequal impact of climate change

on different populations, with marginalised groups—such as low-income communities, racial minorities, and people with disabilities—often facing the greatest risks. Another area for improvement, based on trainer feedback, was the time allocated for audio description sessions. Audio descriptions are critical for making digital content accessible to people with visual impairments. However, trainers observed that students struggled to fully grasp and apply this concept in the allotted time. This finding aligns with broader research, which suggests that accessible design often requires not just theoretical understanding but extensive practice and refinement [15]. Trainers emphasised the need for longer sessions and more hands-on practice to help students internalise the importance of audio descriptions and apply them effectively in their projects.

In summary, the CROMA-GreenSCENT methodology offers a promising approach to integrating accessibility and sustainability within environmental education. Its use of digital tools and interactive, hands-on activities effectively engages students, fostering both enthusiasm and active participation. However, the challenge of making the connection between accessibility and sustainability more explicit remains a key area for improvement. By incorporating clearer, more relatable explanations and real-world examples, alongside extended time for practice in critical areas like audio descriptions, this methodology can further enhance students' understanding and skills. Adopting these refinements will not only promote deeper learning but also ensure that students are empowered to create accessible and sustainable solutions in their future endeavours.

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